

Contemporary Traditional Pottery of the Okabere, Nigeria

Daniel Nosakhare Osariyekemwen & 'Kennedy Jude Eweka

Daniel Nosakhare Osariyekemwen holds a Ph.D. in ceramics and glass and an MFA in ceramics. He presently lectures in the Department of Ceramics, School of General Art and Industrial Design, Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi, Edo State, Nigeria. His main research interest is industrial ceramics and ceramics raw materials development.

Kennedy Jude Eweka holds a Ph.D. and M.F.A. in ceramics. He presently lectures in the Department of Fine and Applied Arts at the University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria. He has conducted researches in ceramics technology.

Abstract:

This field report focuses on the Okabere pottery tradition in Oka, a town located in Ikpoba Okha Local Council Area in Benin City, Nigeria, where potters continue to carry on their age-long practice in a modern world. The potters' clay forms, realized through their unique firing and decorating strategies, are highlighted, as well as their market(ing) structures. This paper shows that the Oka pottery is still very much alive in spite of the influx of modern wares into the local markets, and appears to be in no danger of extinction.

Key words: Okabere pottery, contemporary traditional pottery, pottery production

Introduction

The practice of traditional pottery of the Okabere in Oka community, situated along Benin-Abraka road, approximately twenty kilometers from Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria is an age-long craft. Rigorous but artistically rewarding, almost everybody in each household is involved in the pottery business from making the pots, firing, finishing and marketing them. Usually learned through the apprenticeship system, most women and their children are involved in pottery business to augment the family's earnings. Children and close relatives provide some of the labour needed by helping to carry clay home from the mines and to prepare them for

production. They also help to fetch wood used for firing the pots and equally get involved in similar chores. Their participation in the day-to-day pottery activities gives them the opportunity to learn the process naturally as they mature into adult hood, thereby mastering the craft beside other domestic activities. With the influx of imported enamel wares, China wares, aluminum and plastics utensils in the same markets where the local potters sell their own locally produced wares, there has arisen a keen

Figure 1: An Oka potter at work Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and Kennedy Eweka, 2015,

Figure 3: Sun-drying Oka casseroles Photo: Daniel Osariyekemwen, 2015.

Figure 4: Pre-heating of Oka pots Photo: Daniel Osariyekemwen, 2015

competition, leading to a sharp drop in the sale of their own pots. Yet, the local potters have continued to thrive in spite of the competition they face with imported goods.. This report takes a second look at how the potters continue to engage with their production today and the market links that help them stay afloat.

Pottery Production Today in Oka

The typical Oka potter at work displays a significant dexterity in shaping clay pot employing simple techniques such as paddling, pulling, and pinching. She rolls coils of clay on the soft clay wall to gain height in the pot being moulded. Her workshop can be within her kitchen (Figure 1). When completed, the pots are left to dry in the open grounds of the compound where they can be reached by the sun. (Figures 2 and 3). When the pots are dry, they are then arranged on top of bamboo racks and preheated. The preheated pots are then stacked up, covered round with firewood and set on fire. As the flames gain strength, the pots are covered with old aluminum roofing sheets, so as to retain the heat within the stacked pots to drive out the moisture properly (Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 2: Sun-baking Oka ritual pots Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and Kennedy Eweka, 2015.

The entire firing process takes about two hours. The Okabere potters, like most traditional pottery in the country, still employ the open-air-firing technique which has been used since ancient times. There are no kilns for firing their wares.

The wares are rather covered with splits of bamboo and old corrugated roofing sheets to keep in the heat. During this period, the moisture in the heated pots evaporates in the form of water vapor leaving the pots dry for the actual firing to commence.

Figure 5: Pre-heating in progress
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and Kennedy Eweka, 2015.

Figure 6: Oka potter offloading pre heated pots
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and Kennedy Eweka, 2015.

Figure 7: Oka potters working in group. Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and Kennedy Eweka, 2015.

Figure 8: Oka potters arranging splits of bamboo on the ashes left behind by the preheated fire.
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and Kennedy Eweka, 2015.

Figure 9: Oka potters placing bigger pots in circular formation.
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and Kennedy Eweka, 2015.

Figure 10: Complete stack of preheated pots
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and Kennedy Eweka, 2015

The preliminary firing procedure commences when the potter stacks the wares round a flame made from splits of bamboo. They are pre-heated on their sides to ensure even drying. The bonfire is usually kept low, as these splits of bamboo are not allowed to produce wild flames. The potter monitors and controls the way the stacks of wood or bamboo burns to maintain a steady rate of heating. This is to ensure safety of the stacked pots to reduce incidence of cracks in the pots when the actual firing commences. The preheating removes the physical water or water of plasticity from the pots even though they had been sun-dried. At the end of the pre-heating period, which lasts for about two to three hours, the potters proceed to offload the wares and dismantle the bamboo rack upon which the pots were arranged. They then prepare immediately

for the full firing. A sunny day is usually preferable for the process. The success of the firing process requires the full cooperation of several potters. Each Potter in the various groups brings along with her a bundle of firewood and other related materials that will help make good bonfire. With the combined effort of all, the task becomes easier. To commence the actual firing of the pre-heated pots, the potters arrange splits of bamboo on the ash left behind by the preheated fire. Fresh splits of bamboos are arranged before bigger pots are placed on top in a circular formation to make stacks of pots (Figures 8, 9, 10, and 11). The firing begins just as the pots are stacked on each other on top of the dry wood and completely surrounded with splits of bamboo.

Figure 11:
Partial covering of stacked pots
with splits of bamboo.
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and
Kennedy J Eweka, 2015.

Figure 12:
complete coverage of stacked pots
with splits of bamboo.
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and
Kennedy Eweka, 2015.

Figure 13:
Flaring the Flame
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and
Kennedy J Eweka, 2015

Figure 14:
Final coverage of the pots with old
roofing zinc before full firing
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and
Kennedy Eweka, 2015.

The stacking of the pots starts from the base to form a heap of numerous pots with the bigger and larger pots on the base line together and finally covered with old roofing metal sheets in order to prevent escape of heat from within the stacked up pots (Figures 12, 13, 14 and 15). A great bonfire emerges from the piles of woods surrounding the pots. This most times lasts for an hour. As the flame reduces, a gradual reddish heat is attained beneath the pile. This paper cannot technically establish the maturing temperature attained by Oka potters in their open fire method. However, it can be assumed that if these pots are vitrified enough to serve the end user's need, it may have been within the temperature of 750°C and 800°C. The fired pots are offloaded with the aid of long sticks without allowing them to cool down completely over the heap of ashes. Still red hot, but slightly above 100°C, the pots are boiled in the vegetable dyes poured

on their surfaces. The liquid vanish is usually made from a solution of ground ginger mixed with soaked plantain leaves in a basin of water. They also use the uria, a reddish substance extracted from the bark of a particular tree in the forest, which are soaked for two or three days in water, depending on the maturity of the tree. In its raw state, uria is yellowish in nature. It is boiled for several hours and allowed to cool before the solution is put to use. The solution is not toxic. Interestingly, it produces permanent stains with aesthetic appeal on the pots when applied. Beyond aesthetics, the solution strengthens the pots by further sealing inherent pores or cracks (Figures 16-19). The "uria painting" results in brownish or reddish sheen. On completion of this aesthetic treatment, the pots are stored in a corner of the house in readiness for sale

Figure 16. Oka
Potters applying Uria on cooling
pots
Photo: Jean M. Borgatti and
Kennedy J Eweka, 2015.

Figure 17. Final application of
"Uria" over the pots while still hot
at about a 100°C.
Photo: Daniel Osariyekemwen,
2015.

Figure 18. A container containing the "Uria" vanish Photo: Daniel Osariyekemwen, 2015.

Figure 19: Selected pots are stored in a corner of the house in readiness for sales Photo: Daniel Osariyekemwen, 2015.

Marketability of Oka pots Customers come from different parts of the country to buy the pots. These pots are sold according to their sizes, needs and function. For example, Olokun pots might be smaller but more expensive when compared to the big domestic pots. This is because of its religious function. The potters usually verify whether the pots are well fired before taking them to the market. They do this by using their hands to tap the pots and listen to the sound. Those that ring strongly or emit metallic sounds are selected as first grade. Looking at the amount of labour, materials and time expended on the production of these pots, still they are sold at low prices to buyers. This is one of their strategies for remaining in business inspite of the influence of modern industrial wares. The other is the potters' concentration on wares that remain in demand for local domestic and ritual purposes. These pots are sold in markets outside Edo State and even in places like Onitsha and beyond. The market structure is based on the middle-man distribution channels. The middle men

come to the local market to purchase the pot at wholesale prices directly from the potters and sell to the final buyers. Art collectors also patronize Oka potters. Some of their products are found in museums in Benin City and in private collections. Potters who are not able to transport their products to more distant markets sell their products to other more enterprising potters as middle men who then take the wares to distant markets for sale (Figure 20). Prominent among distant markets where Okabere pots are sold include "Eken" (Okogbo Village Market), Oba market, and the Ikpoba Hill Market near Benin. These are within fourteen to twenty kilometers radius of the pottery centers. The potters (and potter-marketers) carefully load the pots in vehicles in ways that prevent breakage and endeavour to travel with the vehicle to the place where the pots are sold. In the past, it was more difficult to transport wares to the outside markets over the potters' heads, leading to the haulage of only a few pots at a time.

Figure 20: Local Pots displayed at Oba Market, Benin City for sale. Photo: Jean M. Borgotti and Kennedy Eweka, 2015.

Suggested reforms and need for Government intervention

The State and Local Government have in the past intervened with a view to encouraging the local potters. The Nigerian military regimes of the 1980s and early 1990s built centers for the producers of local pots in the two communities of Oka and Okabere both in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State. The inclusion of the communities as tourist centers was germane to the growth of the craft. Sadly, these centers are now dilapidated as a result of neglect and lack of Government support. Since the advent of the civilian administration in 1999 to date there has been no significant policy interventions for the enhancement of the traditional pottery in Okabere in Oka communities.

As a matter of fact, Government should assist these potters, because the craft represents a very important aspect of the country's artistic and material culture. The craft has also provided a source of livelihood to the practitioners. This means that it can readily generate employment opportunities to drive the economy along prosperous lines. These prospects are realizable by the creation of enabling interface between Oka traditional pottery and the Ministry of Commerce and Industry to develop modern methods of production. This may lead to enhanced production and encourage local demand. There is a growing awareness and cultural identity among many Nigerians who have special attachment to their traditional ways, especially local meals which are better prepared and served in locally produced earthenwares. For example, many people have attested to the fact that native pots keep food warm for a longer time and add special flavours to dishes served with them. If the above recommendations are implemented, the downward trend in Oka pottery production will likely be reversed for good.

Conclusion

This field report shows that Oka pottery tradition continues to flourish in spite of the competition from imported plastic, aluminum and china wares. The indigenous knowledge systems that sustain the pottery production continue to be drawn upon by the potters. The potters do not only make wares for local domestic use, they also make decorative wares for modern homes in and around Benin City. Religious needs are also met by the potters as some ritual pots are used in places of traditional worship as receptacles for sacred water, meat and food offering at designated junctions for appeasement of the gods. Historically, some of the pots produced by these potters have served as historical archives as they carry on them icons that record events of historical importance to the existence of the people of Benin Kingdom. Technically the styles of production evolved for century by the potters attest to their specialized techniques which enable them produce sometimes up to twenty pots in two days without engaging the use of any machine. Economically and financially the potters contribute to the economy of their immediate communities. Thus, these underline the Importance and resilience of the Oka pottery tradition.

Acknowledgements:

This field report results mainly from a study visit to Oka community, Ikpoba-Okha Local Government Area of Edo State by the authors who conducted personal interviews with the local potters, especially Madam Egbe Mercy Atiti and Blessing Uyigue. These took place in March 2015. The authors are especially grateful to these potters for their time and co-operation. Some photographs used in this paper are taken from studies conducted in 2015 by Professor Jean M. Borgatti (a Fulbright Scholar 2002-2003, 2014-2016 in the Department of Fine and Applied Arts, University of Benin) and Kennedy J Eweka.

References

Abamwa O.E (2012). Pottery decoration: An identity for the Amai potters of Delta State, Ashakwa Journal of ceramics Vol. 8, pp.123-130.

Areo, M.O. & Areo, A.B. (20011). Technical and technological challenges against pottery in Ilorin, Ashakwa Journal of Ceramics, vol.8 pp.9-19.

Otimeyin P., Osairiyekemwen D. & Ibude, 1. (2011). Historical appraisal of the North Ibie Pottery Culture. Design Review: Journal of Industrial Design. Vol. 2 pp. 112-118.

Saibu, A. (2005): Fundamentals of Ceramics. Benin City: Mara Mon Bros Enterprise.